

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Rajavadlu and Sagar-Samba released in Andhra Pradesh, India

M. Kashikar, N. V. Nanda, V. Hasan, and N. Kulkarni, Rice Section A, Agricultural Research Institute, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

Rajavadlu (RNR99377) and Sagar-Samba (RNR52147) were released in Andhra Pradesh (AP) for general cultivation during 1993.

Rajavadlu, a derivative of the cross Rajendra/IR30, is a semidwarf, medium-duration variety with multiple resistances and high yield potential.

In yield trials under transplanted irrigated conditions from 1980 to 1991, Rajavadlu yielded an average of 6.5 t/ha, with 21% higher yields than Tellahamsa, 34% than Saleem, 55% than Prakash, and 24% than Samba-Mahsuri, one of the most popular varieties in AP.

In the All-India Coordinated Trials, Rajavadlu ranked 2nd and yielded an average 21.2% more than check varieties. In farmers' field trials, it yielded an average of 20% more than the checks.

Rajavadlu is nonlodging, photoperiod-insensitive, and fertilizer-responsive. It has 130-135 d duration in wet season and 145-150 d in dry season due to the region's low temperatures. It is resistant to blast, brown spot, and sheath rot and moderately resistant to bacterial leaf blight and gundhi bug. Seedlings up to 50 d old may be planted without problems. Grain is long and slender with white translucent kernels and good cooking quality.

Sagar-Samba (RNR52147) is another medium-duration nonlodging variety with multiple resistances and fine grains. It is derived from the double cross IR8/Siam 29//IR8/Ptb21.

It was tested in various yield trials under transplanted irrigated conditions from 1974 to 1991. Yield averaged 5.7 t/ha—13.4% higher than that of Samba-Mahsuri. In All-India Coordinated and multilocation trials, Sagar-Samba yielded an average of 5.6 t/ha, an average of 12.4% more than that of check varieties.

In large-scale demonstration trials from 1982 to 1991, Sagar-Samba yielded an average of 4.9 t/ha. In minikit trials, it averaged 4.5 t/ha, an 8.3% increase over the checks.

Sagar-Samba is a dwarf photoperiod-insensitive, fertilizer-responsive variety

with a 145 d duration in wet season. It is resistant to blast, sheath rot, brown spot, and gall midge and has field resistance to brown planthopper. Grain is medium slender. ■

Pakhal: a high-yielding, short-duration rice variety for Hazara division in Pakistan

M. Akram, M. Ashraf, F. M. Abbasi, and M. A. Sagar, National Agricultural Research Centre, Islamabad, Pakistan

Pakhal (IR28128-45-2) is a new high-yielding rice variety recommended for cultivation in Hazara division. It is semidwarf and 104 cm tall, compared with local variety JP5, which is 131 cm. Pakhal matures 16 d earlier than JP5. The new variety produced 28% more grain

Table 1. Performance of Pakhal in yield trials. Pakistan, 1988-90.

Year	Yield (t/ha)		Percentage increase over JP5
	Pakhal	JP5	
1988	3.7	2.9	29
1989	5.5	4.4	25
1990	5.0	3.9	28
Mean	4.7	3.7	27

Table 2. Comparative characteristics of Pakhal and JP5. Pakistan.

Agronomic trait	Pakhal	JP5
Plant height (cm)	104	131
Maturity period (d)	124	140
Yield (t/ha)	4.6	3.3
1,000-grain weight (g)	22.9	24.2
Grain quality (physicochemical characteristics)		
Rough grain		
Length (mm)	10.0	7.8
Breadth (mm)	2.2	4.2
Milled grain		
Length (mm)	6.6	5.8
Breadth (mm)	1.9	3.0
L-B ratio	3.5	1.9
Grain size and shape	Long/slender	Short/bold
Head rice recovery (%)	58.8	55.2
Aroma	None	None
Protein content (%)	8.0	7.8
Amylose content (%)	24.7	17.7

than did JP5 in 1989 and 1990 national uniform rice yield trials (Table 1).

Pakhal is resistant to stem borer and leafhopper. Head rice recovery is 58.8% for Pakhal and 55.2% for JP5 (Table 2). Pakhal's grain is long and slender while that of JP5 is short and bold. Pakhal's quality index value is 2.2; that of JP5 is 0.84. ■

ADT42: a new high-yielding, early-duration rice for Tamil Nadu, India

A. P. M. K. Soundararaj, S. Giridharan, S. Geetha, P. Narayanasamy, A. Abdul Kareem, S. Palanisamy, and S. Chelliah, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TNRRI), Aduthurai 612101, India

ADT42 is a semidwarf indica rice that was developed at TNRRI by pedigree selection from the cross AD9246/ADT29. It is suitable for cultivating as a transplanted crop in the irrigated ecosystem.

In 91 trials conducted at research stations and in farmers' fields in Tamil Nadu, ADT42 yielded a mean of 5.5 t/ha, 10% more than the yield of check IR50 (Table 1).

ADT42 possesses moderate resistance to blast and brown planthopper (BPH) (Table 2).

This variety is 90 cm tall and has a growth duration of 100 d. The grain is long and slender, with good cooking quality. It has hulling recovery of 81.9% and milling recovery of 75.6%. Its 1,000-grain weight is 24.8 g.

ADT42 was released in Jan 1994 for cultivation during kharif season (Jun-Sep) in all districts of Tamil Nadu. ■

Table 1. Grain yield of ADT42 in Tamil Nadu, India. 1986-93.

Trial and year	Locations (no.)	Mean grain yield (t/ha)		Increase over check (%)
		ADT42	IR50 (check)	
TNRRRI, Aduthurai, 1986-93	8	6.0	4.5	33
Multilocation trials at research stations, 1990-92	22	5.5	4.8	15
Adaptive research trials in farmers' fields, 1992	61	5.5	5.2	7
Total/weighted mean	91	5.7	4.8	10

Table 2. Reaction of ADT42 to blast and BPH in Tamil Nadu, India. 1990-92.

Disease/insect	Mean score ^a	
	ADT42	IR50 (check)
Blast	3.4	8.7
BPH	3.7	7.0

^aScored under artificial conditions using the scoring methods in *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

CORH1: the first rice hybrid for Tamil Nadu, India

M. Rangaswamy, M. N. Prasad, S. R. Sree Rangasamy, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore 641003, India; S. S. Virmani, IRRI; E. A. Siddiq, Directorate of Rice Research (DRR), Hyderabad, India; and T. B. Ranganathan, W. Wilfred Manual, K. Thiyagarajan, P. Jayamani, V. Palanisamy, K. Angamuthu, A. S. Ponnusamy, G. James Martin, P. Thangamani, and R. Velusamy, TNAU

CORH1 is a rice hybrid selected at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, from hybrids shared by IRRI through DRR, Hyderabad. The hybrid is developed using the cytoplasmic genetic male sterility and fertility restorer system. IR62829 A and IR10198-66-2 R are the parents.

CORH1 matures in 100-115 d and is up to 75 cm tall. It has high-tillering ability, giving up to 20 productive tillers/hill at 25- x 20-cm spacing. The average grain number is 150/panicle; its 1,000-grain weight is 20 g. Grains are medium slender and straw-colored; kernels are

Yield of CORH1 (t/ha) compared with IR50 and Rasi, Tamil Nadu, India.

Type of trial	Year	Trials (no.)	CORH1 ^a	IR50	Rasi
Research station	1990-92	4	5.2	4.6	-
Multilocation	1991 kharif	7	5.7	4.4	-
Multilocation	1992 kharif	6	5.2	4.8	-
Multilocation	1993 kharif	3	5.4	4.3	-
Large-scale demonstration	1993 kharif	4	5.2	4.9	-
On-farm	1992 kharif	14	6.1	5.2	-
On-farm	1993 kharif	18	6.3	5.4	-
National hybrid rice	1990-91	18	6.2	-	5.1
Mean		74	5.9	5.0	5.1

^a% over IR50 = 118.8; Rasi = 117.3.

white. CORH1 is best suited for May-Jun sowing in Tamil Nadu.

The mean grain yield for CORH1 at 74 locations in research station, on-farm, and national hybrid rice trials (see table) was 5.9 t/ha compared with 5.0 t/ha for IR50. The mean biological yield of CORH1 was 11.2 t/ha (5.9 t grain and 5.3 t straw). The highest recorded grain yield was 10.1 t/ha (see figure).

Physical, cooking, chemical, and organoleptic characters are all good. CORH1 is moderately resistant to whitebacked planthopper, brown

planthopper, green leafhopper, sheath rot, brown spot, and rice tungro virus under field conditions.

The Tamil Nadu State Variety Release Committee approved the release of CORH1 in Dec 93 and the state government released it for general cultivation during kharif season (Jun-Sep) 1994. ■

IRRN REMINDER

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.

Average and highest yield of CORH1, Tamil Nadu, India.